

Gautam, an improved rice variety for winter (boro) season in Bihar, India

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Rice yield during wet season is poor in Bihar, while it is very high in winter (boro) season from Oct-Nov to Apr-May. The area cultivated in northeastern Bihar during winter season is about 0.1 million ha, mostly in low-lying tracts where the water table is high.

Available early- and medium-duration modern varieties and traditional tall boro rice are cultivated. To avoid cold injury, the nursery is raised in Oct-Nov and seedlings are transplanted in Jan-Feb. Seedlings are damaged severely by the cold. Cold tolerance at the seedling stage is required to ensure seedling survival, shorten the growing period, and expand the cropping area.

We screened available local and improved germplasm at Pusa, where temperatures drop to as low as 4 °C. A varietal trial was conducted at different sites to develop a suitable cold-tolerant variety. An EMS-induced mutant from

Table 1. Performance of PSRM1-16-4B-11 in multilocation varietal trials. Bihar, India, 1989-93.

Year	Center	Yield (t/ha)			CV (%)	LSD
		PSRM1-16-4B-11	Boro	Pusa 2-1		
1989-90	Pusa	7.3	5.1	Damaged	12.0	5.6
1990-91	Pusa	7.7	4.2	Damaged	10.7	4.3
	Biraul ^a	3.8	3.0	Damaged	16.4	5.1
1991-92	Katihar	5.7	-	5.4	13.4	3.5
	Pusa	5.3	4.6	Damaged	16.5	6.1
	Biraul	5.5	4.4	Damaged	13.8	4.3
	Katihar ^a	3.4	3.2	2.5	6.8	1.6
1992-93	Agwanpur	5.1	4.1	3.2	9.2	2.5
	Pusa ^b	4.2	3.6	Damaged	-	-
	Biraul ^a	2.5	2.3	Damaged	15.0	2.0
	Agwanpur	4.8	4.0	24.0	11.1	0.3

^aIrrigation water unavailable at critical stage. ^bAv yield only.

Table 2. Performance of PSRM1-16-4B-11 in farmers' field. Bihar, India.

Site	Area (m ²)	Yield (t/ha)
1	90	8.8
2	360	8.3
3	2000	8.1
4	2000	8.6
5	1000	8.1
6	1500	8.3
7	1000	7.2
8	1600	6.6
9	1000	6.5
10 (check)	1000	5.0
11 (check)	1000	5.5
Av	PSRM1-16-4B-11	7.9
	Check	5.2

Rasi, PSRM1-16-4B-11, was found superior in yield and cold tolerance over checks at all locations (Table 1). Yield averaged 7.9 t/ha in farmers' fields (Table 2). This culture was recently released as Gautam.

Gautam is semidwarf, with a high degree of cold tolerance at the seedling stage. It tillers profusely during winter. Its grains are short and fine. ■

Bengawan Solo, a short-duration aromatic rice in Indonesia

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B7136e-Mr-22-1-5 has been released as Bengawan Solo, a short-duration aromatic rice for cultivation under irrigation in Indonesia. This variety is derived from the cross IR56²/IR841. Its plant height, maturity, and yield potential are about the same as those of IR64 (Table 1). Bengawan Solo is resistant to BPH biotype 1. (See Table 2 for important characteristics of Bengawan Solo compared with the local aromatic rice, Pandanwangi.)

Table 1. Plant height, maturity, and yield potential of Bengawan Solo and IR64 in eight provinces in Indonesia.

Province	Location (no.)	Bengawan Solo			IR64		
		Height (cm)	Maturity (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Height (cm)	Maturity (d)	Yield (t/ha)
South Sumatera	4	92	117	4.3	96	119	4.2
Lampung	4	103	109	4.9	97	112	5.1
West Java	5	103	110	5.1	105	113	4.7
Central Java	5	89	122	6.3	82	116	5.7
East Java	5	98	115	6.6	91	117	7.0
Bali	3	115	117	4.4	106	117	4.4
West Nusatenggara	2	99	117	4.4	99	111	4.7
South Sulawesi	5	99	118	4.0	94	118	3.8
Av		99.8	116	5.0	96	115	5.0

Bengawan Solo has good grain quality and strong aroma. Its aromatic trait is maintained across regions, unlike

Pandanwangi, the aromatic trait of which is highly affected by environment. It is therefore grown only in limited areas in